

Artificial Emotional Intelligence: The Thoughtful Integration of A.I. into Human Society

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Abstract

Keywords:

1. Introduction

The word “robot” was coined by the Czech writer Karel Capek, who penned a play entitled, “R.U.R., for Rossum’s Universal Robots. Deriving the word from the Czech word “robota,” meaning “drudgery” or “servitude”, Capek used “robot” to refer to a race of artificial humans who replace human workers in a futurist dystopia. As we integrate Artificial Intelligence into robots and other autonomous systems, what will the relationship between man and machine be? How will machines understand the human experience? How will humans work alongside machines? And how will the human race come to empathize and understand the plight of a future race of automated beings?

2. Aim

To evaluate the question of how to best integrate A.I. into human society to maximize A.I., utility, acceptance, and assimilation into human society if endowed with the ability to understand human emotion.

3. Material and methods

We have conducted multiple studies using both IBM’s Watson and Nvidia’s open source DIGITS, to classify various human emotions to determine a baseline for improving upon the accuracy of models built to implement and/or display artificial emotional intelligence.

4. Results

Thus far, accuracy rates ranged between 90% for emotions such as happiness, and 53% interpreting more complex states, such as sadness, with an error rate of 21%.

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5. Conclusions

According to the results of this study, the best and most ethical way to integrate artificial intelligence and autonomous systems into human society, may not be solely to focus on machines gaining the ability to mimic human behavior or emotion, but rather for machines to understand the human experience through emotion, and adapt its own behavior or reactions based on such emotional intelligence.

6. Keyword

Artificial Intelligence; Emotion; Machine Learning.

Author biography

Ean Mikale is a published author and Dronetreprenuer, creator of a Federally Recognized Apprenticeship Program for Commercial Drone Pilots, current participant of the NVIDIA Inception Program for AI Startups, IBM Global Entrepreneur, member of the National Small Business Association Leadership and Technology Councils, and has been featured in the London-based Global Banking and Finance Review Magazine for his work in social finance. Follow him on LinkedIn, Instagram, and Facebook: @eanmikale